

Relationship between Interpersonal Skills, Analytical Skills and Career Development.

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Abstrac

This research paper help in identifying the relationship between the interpersonal skills, analytical skills and the career development in the private banks of Karachi. To collect the data purposive sampling was used and questionnaires were filled from the 30 managers of different levels in different private banks. There is a positive relationship between the interpersonal skills, analytical skills and the career development. At each level it has positive effect. This research will help the management to make workforce more effective by knowing the basic tools for career development at different managerial levels that directly impact on the productivity and performance of the overall organization.

Keywords: *Interpersonal skills, analytical skills, career development, relationship, self-grooming.*

INTRODUCTION

The objective of the study is to find out the relationship between the interpersonal skills, analytical skills and career development at different levels of the management in the private banks of Karachi. Interpersonal skill and analytical skills perform crucial part to enhance career development in the organization. Career development is related to the sequence of positions that a person hold during his lifetime (Robins, 2004). As time passes environment is constantly in changing mode so the field of the career development in the organization have so much importance for the efficient working of the workforce. Career development is the career-enhancement (Kram, 1980). With the change in response time and speedy work the need of the skillful workforce increased that adopt the uncertainties and manage the personality. It is related to the career advancement and personal growth (Clawson, 1979; Kram, 1985; Levinson, 1978; Phillips-Jones, 1982). It means the adaptability of multicultural context and uncertainties (Harvey & Hammer, 1999). Managers work with different people and in different environment so to respond the market required interpersonal skills and analytical skills that help in managing it with different things and good decision making by evaluating the situation in the future uncertainties. Relationship with bosses subordinates and peers (Kram, 1985; Levinson, 1978). Best evaluation of the situation by the managers at different levels is very important for the efficient working of the overall organization. Ability to think and to conceptualize the about abstract and complex situation (Robins, 2004). Abilities enable people to understand the complex inter-relationship between the organization's component parts and to see the organization within the context of its environment (Bovee, Thill, Wood & Doovel, 1995). These skills can be enhanced by providing particular knowledge, training, and motivation etc. If these skills are improved, the organization will be more profitable, efficient and flexible. Career development and skills are important not only in the organization but in the whole life of an individual. If workforce (nation) is confident in every situation it leads towards the development of the economy of the country. This research will help the management to make workforce more effective by knowing the basics tools for career development at different managerial levels that directly impact on the productivity and performance of the overall organization.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK:

Hypothesis

H₁: At different levels of the management interpersonal

Skills and analytical skills would have positive effect on the career development of managers in the private banks of Karachi.

H₁₀: At different levels of the management interpersonal

Skills and analytical skills would not have positive effect on the career development of managers in private banks of Karachi.

Literature Review

Organization work to fulfill the needs of the nation. The working of the organization is based on the workforce that how much they are efficient and change the individuals according to the uncertainties. Adaptability of multicultural context and uncertainties is correlated with the career development of individuals (Harvey & Hammer, 1999). In organizations at different levels and at different departments, we need different sort of skills to manage effectively. The organizations that are not efficient having the workforce that is de-motivated and development process of individual is very low. Individual career development is based on the work. Teamwork improves the self-grooming and also shows that it has direct effect on the performance levels of the development process (Paglis, 2010). For career development in the organization at Different levels of organization required different type of skills. In professional life different type of skills are needed that give the ability to fit in the changing environment and enhance career development of individuals. Keys for the career success and survival in the organization lead toward the development of organization and managers are: excellent performance record, communication skills, interpersonal skills, personality, technical skill, Significant work experience, handle stress, ability to make difficult decision, power and mentor (Simonetti, 1999). Skills are very important in career development of a manager. Basically skills required at different levels of managers that lead towards the career development that was not explained. Management development was directly linked with the effectiveness of different levels of managers with analytical and self-related skills, people related skills and task oriented skills (Labaf, Analoui & Cusworth, 1996). The earlier studies only focused on the workforce and manager's career development not at all levels. In organization at top levels skills are consider important to enhance career development that is directly linked with organization's performance.

Interpersonal skills (Peer relationship, working in diverse condition) and analytical skills (Decision making) are very important in every level of management. Many excellent contributors have focused on the cultural changing in career development (Bingham & Ward, 1997; & Hartung, 1997; Subich, 1996). But in this research we focused the effect of changing environment (technology) at different levels of management in which they perform the duty. To fit in the present situation interpersonal skills have a great importance because everything going in the organization effect directly or indirectly the workforce efficiency that leads towards the overall organization performance. If workforce knows its value then easily judge the values of others and make good and strong relationships. Peer relationship in the lack of hierarchical organization easier to achieve communication, mutual support and collaboration (Karm & Isabella, 1985).

It relates to handle the people in team work and under supervision of you in different conditions. Career development is not taking place in every relation; trust is the main thing that strong the relations and from where individual enhance career development. Career development related to the nature of relationship with peers (Karm & Isabella, 1985). Relation between teams is based on team trust and individual trust (Yuchun Xiao, Xiyang Zheng, Wenan Pan & Xiaoxia Xie, 2010). Interpersonal skills are also very important factor in the development of the career specifically in the banking sector. It's important to ensure that the workforce is well equipped and improves career development with the desired knowledge and skills to be competitive and to remain succeed in the economy (Baumard, 2002). Knowledge is essential for decision making and evaluation of situation in special environment that help to increase the thinking process and career development of managers. Knowledge gives confidence and efficiency in work. Knowledge related skills required mostly at top levels in organizations. In this research we discuss that how these skills (factors) are effective at different levels of managers that enhance the career development.

Career development directly link with the development of personality and broadening the thoughts of managers in his work life that have direct impact on the overall organization's performance. Career development is the most important factor for manager in the organization for self motivation. With the ability of the career development a manager can achieve his goal very efficient manner. Career development directly link with the development of personality and broadening the thoughts of managers in his work life. There should be proper environment for the career development in the organization. Keys for the career success (development process) and survival in the organization lead toward the development of organization and managers are: excellent performance record, communication skills (Simonetti, 1999). For career development different types of the abilities should be there in the manager's personality that in the business language said skills.

In life adult relationships directly encourage, support and contribute to progress in life and career, in work setting many relationship meet with career development Karm, 1985; Levinson 1978). Career development is very important for the efficient work of the manager who gives the positive results towards the achievement of the organizational goal.

Research Methodology

The type of scale that was used for this research was the interval scale and the scaling technique that is used in it is the Liker scale with the seven options that were strongly disagree, somewhat disagree, disagree, unsure, agree, somewhat agree and strongly agree was develop considering the different dimensions of the interpersonal skills, analytical skills and career development in the organization at different managerial levels. Interpersonal skills can be measured by working with diverse condition (technology change) and peer relationship, it was checking by seeing that how the manager give response to the new technology in performing the office work and set within the continuously changing environment in sense of technology. It was also measured by checking that how a manager having relationship with his peer, bosses and subordinate within the organization. Analytical skill was measured by decision making and seeing the effect that how manager took decisions in the organization. Career development was measured by self grooming in which manager took the positive things from the other personalities and adopt them to improve himself at the current position in the organization. In order to check and ensure that the scale developed actually measured the concepts then various statistical tools were performed on the items of the scale.

In this research the non probability sampling technique is use and in that purposive sampling is used. Purposive sampling is used when researcher has a specific purpose.

Reasons for using purposive sampling are:

- When population size is small and not so much large
- When the proper sources of databases are absent. It means the secondary data is not available.
- In the research question ask for the specific purpose. Mean it also depend upon the type of research question

The data collection approach is questionnaire and filled by the specified units through personal visit. The study consists of the 30 sample size data that was only collected from Karachi. In this research we used the non probability sampling and the

Sampling technique is purposive to select the data because the size of the sample is not so much large. First the questionnaire was developed on the basis of the concepts and measure through different variable's dimensions by creating the items according to that.

Results

The following table is calculated for the measurement of Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items which is .888. This Cronbach's Alpha shows that the results of the data have reliability up to a significant level. It's a good sign for a researcher to work on the project and further work on this data.

Reliability Statistics

TABLE: 1

The reliability analysis of Cronbach's Alpha (N=30)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of items
.888	30

The measurement of mean, median, mode, standard deviation and variances are the elements of descriptive study for the data. These calculations are basically done in order to measure the variation in our data. The following table shows the values of mean, standard deviation and variance of the scale items designed in order to test the impact of interpersonal skills(Work with changing Technology, Peer Relationship),Analytical skills (Decision Making)on Career Development(Self Grooming).

TABLE: 2 Descriptive statistics

	N	Min	Maxi	Mean	Std.Deviation
IPS1	30	1	6	4.57	1.382
IPS2	30	2	6	4.53	1.196
IPS3	30	2	6	4.17	1.341
IPS4	30	2	6	4.53	1.279
IPS5	30	1	6	4.30	1.418
IPS6	30	2	6	4.43	1.278
IPS7	30	1	6	4.20	1.349
IPS8	30	1	6	3.97	1.351
IPS9	30	1	6	4.37	1.450
IPS10	30	2	6	4.80	1.095
AS11	30	2	6	4.63	1.273
AS12	30	2	6	4.40	1.245
AS13	30	2	6	4.57	1.223
AS14	30	2	6	4.23	1.251
AS15	30	2	6	4.53	1.074
AS16	30	1	6	4.53	1.306
AS17	30	2	6	4.23	1.135
AS18	30	2	6	4.60	1.102
AS19	30	2	6	4.60	1.248
AS20	30	2	6	4.47	1.224
CD21	30	1	6	4.07	1.311
CD22	30	2	6	4.07	1.066
CD23	30	1	6	4.37	1.380
CD24	30	1	6	4.60	1.450
CD25	30	1	6	4.03	1.392
CD26	30	1	6	3.38	1.299
CD27	30	2	6	4.37	1.165
CD28	30	2	6	4.28	1.126
CD29	30	3	6	4.20	.935
CD30	30	2	6	4.57	1.006

Correlation Matrix Interpersonal Skills (Work with changing Technology, Peer Relationship), Analytical Skills Decision Making) on Career Development (Self Grooming).The said values of the calculated person correlation depicts that there is a highly positive relation among variables of the study.

TABLE: 3
Correlation matrix of variables (N=30)

	CD	IPS	AS
CD	1.00	.628	.688
IPS	.628	1.00	.648
AS	.688	.648	1.00
N(CD)	30	30	30
N(IPS)	30	30	30
N(AS)	30	30	30

Correlations is significant at 0.05 level (1-tailed)

Results show that there is a positive relationship between interpersonal skills, conceptual skills & Career Development. It can be concluded that if we make changes in interpersonal skills, analytical skills so this will also have strong effect on Career Development. For this reason, we can say that there is a strong positive relationship between interpersonal skills, conceptual skills & Career Development. But we cannot generalize this result on any other population of the world.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Skills are very important for a manager's career. If managers are skilled they move towards the career development. But career development is effected by the interpersonal skills and the analytical skills differently at every level of management.

Effectiveness of managers is highly depends largely on their ability and desire for their own personal growth and development in career in the organization. Skills have positive effect on the career development of the managers in the organizations but at top level of management it is more affected and enhanced. The present study is one of the initial studies in Pakistan on the concerned topic. The research can help researchers to explore new areas in this topic and understand the role of interpersonal skills and the analytical skills on the career development in the organizations. To extend the research in this topic the researcher should focused on the overall population in the Pakistan because Pakistan has different type of cultures in different areas that should have interesting findings in future.

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